

Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach Result Reproduction

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Abstract

Reproducibility is key for scientific research. It enables not only the validation of findings but enhances the building on existing knowledge. The goal of this report is to reproduce the findings of the paper "Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach", by Shen et al. [3]. We will present our workflow reproducing the results presented by the authors of the original paper. Thereby, we are comparing the findings and checking whether the proposed SetRank algorithm is in fact significantly better than the baseline algorithms. Additionally, we will outline encountered problems while trying to reproduce the setup and report on measures we took to tackle those. Based on our analysis we are not able to confirm that the proposed algorithm significantly outperforms the baselines, due to the lack of knowledge on the optimal hyperparameters.

Keywords: Entity-Set Aware Search, Unsupervised Ranking Model, Unsupervised Model Selection, Literature Search, Reproducibility, Reproduction

1 Introduction

Reproducibility is a desired characteristic of a research result. Not solely for the perk of validity of the research but for the possibility of transferring the approach to other research domains or further building on the gained knowledge. In order to achieve reproducibility in computer science research, it is often necessary to publish the code alongside the results in a paper. As this is not often the case, reproducing results in an IT dominated domain can be cumbersome.

In this paper, our goal is to reproduce the results reported by Shen et al. [3], who presented an entity-aware search algorithm for the research domain¹. Luckily, for the sake of reproducing the findings, the authors published their code in a GitHub repository², as well as further information on

how to run the code and reproduce the environment they used for their research. Furthermore, the data they used is also cited in the GitHub repository. Although the authors spent time documenting their work, not all information is present to reproduce all findings reported in the paper. The necessary steps to repeat the analysis and our findings will be the content of the rest of the report.

This report is structured as follows. Firstly, we will summarize the experimental setup of the original paper and thereby include the necessary notions to understand the setting of the analysis in Section 2. Afterwards, in Section 3 the necessary steps to execute the project are listed including the changes that need to be made to the code, in order to make it executable. Section 4 focuses on the evaluation, comparing our findings to the results reported by the authors of the original paper. Furthermore, we will list the core issues we encountered during the analysis in Section 5. These include common problems that are transferable to other studies and are encountered often when reproducing papers. In the end, Section 6 will focus on a summary of the differences observed and adjustments we had to make.

2 Experimental Setup

Two different datasets were used for the experiments. One was obtained from Xiong et al. [5] and contains queries from semantic scholar's log. The dataset consists of 100 queries. Fourteen of them are entity-set queries.

The second dataset includes 100 queries from biologists. 86 of them are entity-set queries. As they were not annotated, PubTator [4] was used to retrieve the entity information.

The authors compare their approach to four other baseline ranking models, namely Vector Space Model (BM25) [2], Query Likelihood Model with Dirichlet Prior smoothing (LM-DIR) or Jelinek Mercer smoothing (LM-JM) [6] and Information-Based model (IB) [1].

The SetRank algorithm has five hyperparameters that need to be tuned. These include weights to balance the importance of the different text fields like the title or abstract. Similarly, the balance between words and entities in the queries is tuned.

They compute statistical significance using a two-tailed t-test with an α value of 0.05. The experiment setup is based

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¹Original Paper: doi.org/10.1145/3209978.3210055

²Repository: <https://github.com/jmshen1994/SetRank>

on a five-fold CV, where four of the folds are used to apply a grid search to search for the optimal parameters for the models (e.g., field weights) and the remaining one is used as a test set on the final model.

The parameters tested in the grid search can be seen in Table 1.

The performance measurements used are the NDCG (Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain) and the MAP (Mean Average Precision) with the former being reported in the paper. NDCG is used on 4 levels (5, 10, 15, 20) to compare the different baseline algorithms to SetRank.

3 Executing the Project

The authors have uploaded their project to a public GitHub repository, which can be cloned easily. We can find a *requirements.txt* file which, according to the *README.md* should include all the requirements.

Afterwards, it is still necessary to install ElasticSearch because it needs to run locally in parallel. The dependency to be found in the requirements file is only for Python. We installed it according to the ElasticSearch documentation³.

To start ElasticSearch, it is necessary to call the *elasticsearch.bat* file (we did this using Java 11, after getting an error using Java 15). Both, the OpenJDK and the standard distribution from Oracle of Java 11, work in this context. In order to run ElasticSearch on the localhost, one has to execute the *elasticsearch.bat* file in the *bin* folder. It is important that the folder has a path that does not include a whitespace (at least on Windows). The command below runs ElasticSearch on localhost if executed in the parent folder, in this case *elasticsearch-5.4.0* (the necessary version is stated in the requirements file).

```
.\bin\elasticsearch.bat
```

Furthermore, we ran the project using Python 3.7, which is not mentioned anywhere, though. In the *pytrec_eval* folder there is a README file stating that the module was developed under 3.5. We first tried it using Python 3.9, which did not work.

Then, the index for ElasticSearch needs to be created (this applies to both the baselines and SetRank). It is therefore necessary to run the *create_index.py* files (either in the *code/baselines* subdirectories or *SetRank*). Afterwards, the data needs to be indexed via the *index_data.py* files, which can be found in the same directories as the *create_index.py* ones.

However, in order to run those files, the *s2_doc.json* and *trec_doc.json* need to be added to the respective data folders (either S2-CS or TREC). Those can be downloaded from

Google Drive (TREC⁴) or the Website mentioned in the README file to download the S2-CS data⁵.

3.1 SetRank

For executing SetRank, it is necessary to run the *create_index.py* and *index_data.py* files. This can be done with the commands below:

```
# TREC-BIO
python create_index_TREC.py
python index_data_TREC.py
# S2-CS
python create_index_ESR.py
python index_data_ESR.py
```

Afterwards, according to the README file, it is necessary to execute the *setRank_TREC.py* file with the command shown below.

```
python setRank_TREC.py -query
↪ ../../data/TREC-BIO/trec_query.json
↪ -output ../../results/trec/setRank.run
```

If we do that, we get an error because some paths in the file are incorrect. Therefore, we have to make changes in line 381 and line 385 and change the path from *TREC_Bio* to *TREC-BIO*.

This command works very similarly for the S2-CS dataset.

Afterwards, we can execute the script and get results, to be evaluated (see Section 3.3). Still, there is no explanation on how to retrieve the word, entity and combined results. In contrast to evaluating the baselines (see Section 3.2), there is no additional parameter to be passed on.

Due to not having the possibility to change the mode between word, entity or both, we took a closer look into the code. We realised, that there are additional parameters, namely *consider_entity_set* and *consider_word_set*. Both of them were set to 1.0 initially. By adapting these parameters, we were able to switch between the different modes. For changing the SetRank search engine algorithm to the mode *entity*, we changed the *consider_word_set* to 0. This can be seen for the S2-CS dataset in the command below.

³<https://www.elastic.co/guide/en/elasticsearch/reference/current/install-elasticsearch.html>

⁴<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/15RqULDGONFfiaOyv40ApKMNEL4vS4V-?usp=sharing>

⁵<http://data.allenai.org/esr/>

Table 1. Parameters for Grid Search

Parameter	Values
Field weights (title, abstract)	{1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 50}
Dirichlet smoothing parameter μ	{500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, 3000}
Jelinek Mercer smoothing parameter λ	{0.1, 0.2,..., 0.9}
Relative weight entity token λ_E	{0, 0.1,..., 1}

```
python setRank_ESR.py -query
↳ ../../data/S2-CS/s2_query.json -output
↳ ../../results/s2/setRank_s2_word_new.run
↳ -params title:20.0, abstract:5.0,
↳ keyphrase:16.0,
↳ title_ana:20.0,abstract_ana:5.0,
↳ keyphrase_ana:16.0, bodytext_ana:1.0,
↳ title_mu:1000.0, abstract_mu:1000.0,
↳ keyphrase_mu:1000.0, title_ana_mu:1000.0,
↳ abstract_ana_mu:1000.0,
↳ keyphrase_ana_mu:1000.0,
↳ bodytext_ana_mu:1000.0, entity_lambda:0.5,
↳ type_interaction:1.0,
↳ consider_entity_set:1.0,
↳ consider_word_set:0.0, consider_type:1.0,
↳ word_dependency:1.0
```

Just considering *word* works very similarly (just set the *consider_entity_set* to 0 instead of the other one). Additionally, for executing the script with the other dataset it is just necessary to change to the *setRank_TREC.py* file and pass *trec_query.json* as a parameter.

Furthermore, in the README file in *SetRank/code* it states that the optimal hyperparameters can be obtained by running the *autoSetRank_ESR.py* or *autoSetRank_TREC.py* file respectively. When we do so, however, we lose the connection to ElasticSearch after some time. We think that this was caused by using an external HDD due to some storage space problems.

3.2 Baselines

For the baselines, it is necessary to run the *create_index.py* and *index_data.py* files, as described above. Afterwards, it is possible to run *search_data.py*. The respective commands are shown below. It is necessary to only use one of the values given in the brackets respectively.

```
python create_index.py -sim ['tfidf', 'bm25',
↳ 'lm_jm', 'lm_dir', 'ib']
python index_data.py -sim ['tfidf', 'bm25',
↳ 'lm_jm', 'lm_dir', 'ib']
python search_data.py -sim ['tfidf', 'bm25',
↳ 'lm_jm', 'lm_dir', 'ib'] -mode ['both',
↳ 'word', 'entity']
```

This results in different *.run* files being created, which we evaluated subsequently.

3.3 Evaluation

The authors use *pytrec_eval* (see ⁶) to evaluate the results. *Pytrec_eval* is a python interface for TREC's evaluation tool (see ⁷). It was developed using Python 3.5. The development headers (see ⁸) are necessary to run the evaluation and need to be installed separately. We were then able to run the evaluation with the following command.

```
./eval.sh ../../results/s2/setRank.run setRank
```

This has to be done for every single file independently, which returns a *.tmp* and *.tsv* file. The *.tsv* file contains the results and, when scrolling down, we get to a row called "all", which contains the final results, which can be found on page 572 in the paper.

The *.tmp* file is just a temporary file that is not needed to evaluate the results any further.

3.4 Significance Testing

The *pytrec-eval* repository contains a file for significance testing, which was reused by us. The file can be found in the following directory⁹.

The python file can be executed using the following command. The first parameter links to the respective dataset (either in the TREC directory or S2). The other two parameters contain the path to the *.run* files of the two versions to be compared.

```
cd pytrec_eval/examples
python statistical_significance.py
↳ ../../data/S2-CS/s2.qrel
↳ ../../results/s2/baselines/bm25_both.run
↳ ../../results/s2/setRank.run
↳ --measure='ndcg_cut'
```

Unfortunately, running the script this way leads to an error. It is therefore necessary to change the *args.measure*

⁶https://github.com/cvangysel/pytrec_eval

⁷https://github.com/usnistgov/trec_eval

⁸<https://docs.pwntools.com/en/stable/install/headers.html>

⁹https://github.com/jmshen1994/SetRank/blob/master/pytrec_eval/examples/statistical_significance.py

variable to `ndcg_cut_[5, 10, 15, 20]` before line 47. Therefore, it is quite cumbersome to run all significance tests.

Afterwards, the significance testing can be executed for every method with different measurement variables (we chose `ndcg_cut_[5, 10, 15, 20]`, as this has been used by the authors as well).

Table 2 shows the respective p-values. In our testing, we compared all the different baselines and modes (both, entity, word) with the results of SetRank. This was done for both datasets.

4 Evaluation

4.1 Results

We evaluated all results of the baselines and the SetRank search algorithm. We offer our results in Table 4. On the left side, you can see the used datasets (S2-CS or TREC-BIO) and the normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDSG). The NDSG is a measurement for the ranking quality used for measuring the effectiveness of searching engines. We have grouped the four baselines and the SetRank searching algorithm and listed the results separately for each search type (word, entity or both). For a better comparison between our results and the results from the author, we want to show their resulting table 3 here again.

Moreover, we decided to create a Table 5 to show the absolute difference between our results and the given results from the author. All fields with red background show that there is a difference between the results. A value greater than zero means that our test produced a worse result than the authors', otherwise, negative numbers mean that the tested ranking measurement from us returned a better results than the result from the authors.

In the table, we can see that all results from the baselines, especially from the S2-CS dataset, are extremely similar. Mostly there is a difference smaller than 0.001. Unfortunately, the SetRank search engine algorithm resulted in a bigger difference. For the dataset S2-CS, we usually encountered a difference of less than 0.03 and for the dataset TREC-BIO, we got a different score between 0.027 and 0,075.

As we were not able to run the `autoSetRank.py` files, we suspect that the different results are due to the respective parameters not being tuned again. We first believed that this would not make any difference because the GitHub repository might already be initialised with the author's final parameters, but we have reason to believe that, unfortunately, they might differ.

4.2 Significance Testing

After executing t-tests to compute the significance, we summarised the results in Table 2. The results can be found for each dataset separately and for `NDCG@[5, 10, 15, 20]`, similar as has been done in the paper. The values that are shown

represent the p-values and significantly different values with $\alpha = 0.05$ were marked red.

When comparing BM25 to our SetRank results, it can be observed that the results overall were significantly better than the ones obtained by BM25. This can be seen when considering the "entity" column. When looking at the dataset S2 and column "both" and only the top five or ten queries, the results were not significantly different though.

Another thing that can be observed is that the results for the TREC dataset and column "word" were not significantly different at all and led to very high p-values.

When comparing the results of IB to SetRank, it can be seen that the results for "both" and "word" are mostly not significantly different and lead to p-values bigger than 0.07. Still, the results for the "entity" columns are significantly different, which can especially be observed when comparing the results of the TREC dataset.

Moreover, the results obtained from LM-DIR for the S2 dataset are all significantly different again. However, the results on the TREC dataset and "both" and "word" seem to be quite similar and do not provide any significant difference. The "entity" column is, however, again significantly different.

Lastly, the LM-JM method did not provide any significant differences when looking at only `NDCG@5` or `NDCG@10` for "both" and "word" but the results did significantly differ from the ones obtained with SetRank for `NDCG@5` or `NDCG@10` (with the exception of "word" on the TREC dataset). We did, however, again observe significantly different results when looking only at "entity".

Altogether, one pattern that we could observe when running the significance tests was that the entity column seemed to always lead to significantly different results. The results of the other two methods seemed to depend on the baseline a lot.

5 Issues

5.1 Many README Files

The repository contains about four different README files and it is very difficult to retrieve the required information because it is split up into so many different files.

It might therefore be favourable to just stick to one longer README file, to make it easier to reproduce the results.

5.2 Missing Versions

We had a lot of difficulties finding and installing the required versions. We installed the requirements according to the `requirements.txt` file and started creating the indexes and producing the results, which was already difficult because of an old ElasticSearch version.

Thereafter, we started with `pytrec_eval`, which requires Python 3.5, where we had to change our python environment, which was again a lot of effort. It would have been a lot better to specify all the dependencies and versions beforehand.

5.3 404-Error on GitHub

When recreating the baselines, the authors link to a different GitHub repository, with the remark that the code can be used to change the hyperparameters used for the baselines (the link can be found in ¹⁰).

However, the link (see ¹¹) leads to a 404-error though. This makes it impossible for us to change the hyperparameters and, therefore, we had to stick to the ones the authors provided.

5.4 Datasets

As already mentioned, one of the datasets can be found on Google Drive. Still, in the commit history, it can be seen that the path to the Google Drive file has changed, and the current file was last updated in November 2021. We do not know whether the data was changed or just moved to a different location but they should have documented that (especially since we needed to access the data to download the *trec_doc.json* files as described in Section 3).

Additionally, when accessing and downloading the S2 dataset, we made the observation that the *s2.qrel* file contains about 300 more data points than the one from the website does. The authors do not give any information on why this is the case.

5.5 Hyperparameter Tuning for SetRank

According to the README file in the original repository, the SetRank algorithm can be executed by just creating the index, indexing the data and then running the *setRank_ESR.py* or *setRank_TREC.py* file respectively.

However, according to the README file in the "code" subdirectory, the execution of the SetRank algorithm also includes running the *autoSetRank_ESR.py* or *autoSetRank_TREC.py* file respectively. The two scripts will tune the hyperparameters, which can afterwards be used to run the mentioned *setRank_xxx.py* files.

In our opinion, the authors should have provided one clear process to follow, instead of providing two different ones.

6 Conclusion

In this report, we analyzed the findings reported by Shen et al., in the paper Entity Set Search of Scientific Literature: An Unsupervised Ranking Approach, regarding their reproducibility. Since the authors made their source code for this research available, it was possible to investigate if the reported results match the performance of the implemented algorithms.

In the beginning, recreating the environment was a major obstacle as the authors did not specify a Python version. Furthermore, slight adjustments to the code were necessary

in order to make it executable. When rerunning the baseline algorithms, we obtained similar results (differences only observable starting at the third or fourth decimal place) as the authors, which assured us that our setup is comparable.

However, the results for the SetRank algorithm were not comparable using the default parameters in the repository. This may be because the parameters were not tuned the same way the original authors did. Therefore, we could not confirm the hypothesis that the SetRank algorithm significantly outperforms all other baseline algorithms to which it was compared in the paper. Additionally, we could not further investigate the setting of only comparing entity-set-queries because this subset of queries was not documented well enough to reproduce it.

We published our code and results on a public GitHub repository, which can be accessed following this link¹².

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¹⁰<https://github.com/jmshen1994/SetRank/tree/master/code>

¹¹<https://gist.github.com/mickeystroller/a2134d96fb1a67cea4b5bc5cd7c4afe3>

¹²https://github.com/verryshadow/ExpDesign_SetRank

Dataset	Method	BM25 - SetRank			LM-DIR - SetRank			LM-JM - SetRank			IB - SetRank		
		Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both
S2-CS	NDCG@5	0.0590	0.0069	0.1372	0.0198	0.0268	0.0079	0.2875	0.0273	0.0790	0.7716	0.0195	0.2595
	NDCG@10	0.0529	0.0007	0.3854	0.0002	0.0002	0.0078	0.0306	0.0005	0.1182	0.7716	0.0002	0.2230
	NDCG@15	0.0066	0.0000	0.0168	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0191	0.0001	0.0258	0.0423	0.0000	0.1044
	NDCG@20	0.0011	0.0000	0.0114	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0039	0.0000	0.0176	0.0402	0.0000	0.0394
TREC-BIO	NDCG@5	0.3534	0.0000	0.0226	0.7119	0.0000	0.0455	0.9578	0.0000	0.2003	0.7157	0.0000	0.0986
	NDCG@10	0.3380	0.0000	0.0236	0.4220	0.0000	0.1113	0.7563	0.0000	0.0939	0.5213	0.0000	0.1518
	NDCG@15	0.5026	0.0000	0.0198	0.4207	0.0000	0.2382	0.6172	0.0000	0.0354	0.4758	0.0000	0.1240
	NDCG@20	0.4715	0.0000	0.0259	0.3316	0.0000	0.3739	0.6508	0.0000	0.0402	0.5463	0.0000	0.0726

Table 2. Significance Tests Baselines vs. SetRank

Dataset	Method	BM25			LM-DIR			LM-JM			IB			SetRank		
		Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both									
S2-CS	NDCG@5	0.3476	0.3319	0.3675	0.3447	0.3460	0.3563	0.3626	0.3394	0.3625	0.3759	0.3420	0.3729	0.3890	0.3761	0.4207*
	NDCG@10	0.3785	0.3520	0.4039	0.3623	0.3579	0.3901	0.3774	0.3519	0.3962	0.3903	0.3557	0.4009	0.4168	0.3885	0.4431*
	NDCG@15	0.4001	0.3616	0.4160	0.3781	0.3673	0.4077	0.4051	0.3666	0.4174	0.4113	0.3699	0.4272	0.4411	0.4054	0.4762*
	NDCG@20	0.4126	0.3752	0.4333	0.4012	0.3816	0.4205	0.4182	0.3804	0.4362	0.4295	0.3855	0.4421	0.4674	0.4229	0.4950*
TREC-BIO	NDCG@5	0.3189	0.1542	0.2613	0.3053	0.1755	0.2669	0.2957	0.1656	0.2826	0.3045	0.1842	0.2770	0.3417	0.2111	0.3744*
	NDCG@10	0.2968	0.1488	0.2472	0.2958	0.1601	0.2571	0.2742	0.1588	0.2572	0.2918	0.1715	0.2633	0.3165	0.1976	0.3522*
	NDCG@15	0.2833	0.1424	0.2395	0.2852	0.1579	0.2591	0.2642	0.1575	0.2437	0.2835	0.1664	0.2541	0.3017	0.1931	0.3363*
	NDCG@20	0.2739	0.1419	0.2337	0.2781	0.1558	0.2547	0.2560	0.1534	0.2362	0.2722	0.1628	0.2406	0.2900	0.1885	0.3246*

Table 3. Original Results from the Paper

Dataset	Method	BM25			LM-DIR			LM-JM			IB			SetRank		
		Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both									
S2-CS	NDCG@5	0.3476	0.3319	0.3675	0.3447	0.3460	0.3563	0.3626	0.3394	0.3625	0.3759	0.3420	0.3729	0.3809	0.3852	0.3897
	NDCG@10	0.3785	0.3520	0.4039	0.3623	0.3579	0.3901	0.3774	0.3519	0.3962	0.3903	0.3557	0.4009	0.4076	0.4122	0.4145
	NDCG@15	0.4001	0.3619	0.4160	0.3781	0.3673	0.4077	0.4051	0.3666	0.4174	0.4113	0.3699	0.4272	0.4370	0.4333	0.4422
	NDCG@20	0.4126	0.3751	0.4333	0.4018	0.3808	0.4204	0.4182	0.3794	0.4357	0.4294	0.3862	0.4421	0.4531	0.4525	0.4595
TREC-BIO	NDCG@5	0.3189	0.1529	0.2599	0.3053	0.1755	0.2669	0.2977	0.1655	0.2826	0.3045	0.1842	0.2770	0.2965	0.2825	0.3093
	NDCG@10	0.2978	0.1486	0.2471	0.2955	0.1601	0.2571	0.2740	0.1588	0.2575	0.2915	0.1715	0.2633	0.2799	0.2724	0.2872
	NDCG@15	0.2833	0.1420	0.2394	0.2852	0.1579	0.2591	0.2641	0.1584	0.2437	0.2836	0.1664	0.2541	0.2721	0.2615	0.2784
	NDCG@20	0.2738	0.1413	0.2336	0.2781	0.1558	0.2544	0.2558	0.1538	0.2362	0.2722	0.1628	0.2410	0.2628	0.2558	0.2689

Table 4. Our Results on Baselines and SetRank

Dataset	Method	BM25			LM-DIR			LM-JM			IB			SetRank		
		Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both	Word	Entity	Both
S2-CS	NDCG@5	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0081	-0.0091	0.0310
	NDCG@10	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0092	-0.0237	0.0286
	NDCG@15	0.0000	-0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0041	-0.0279	0.0340
	NDCG@20	0.0000	0.0001	0.0000	-0.0006	0.0008	0.0001	0.0000	0.0010	0.0005	0.0001	-0.0007	0.0000	0.0143	-0.0296	0.0355
TREC-BIO	NDCG@5	0.0000	0.0013	0.0014	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0020	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0452	-0.0714	0.0651
	NDCG@10	-0.0010	0.0002	0.0001	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0002	0.0000	-0.0003	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	0.0366	-0.0748	0.0650
	NDCG@15	0.0000	0.0004	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0001	-0.0009	0.0000	-0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0296	-0.0684	0.0579
	NDCG@20	0.0001	0.0006	0.0001	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	0.0002	-0.0004	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0004	0.0272	-0.0673	0.0557

Table 5. Difference Between the Author's results and our Results